

Synthesis of 3-Substituted Coumarins. Part II

D. Chakravarti, R. Das and Sambhunath Chakravarti

A number of 3-amino and 3-hydroxy coumarins substituted in the phenyl ring have been synthesised. The synthesis of halogenated aldehydes required for the present work has also been described.

Chakravarti and Das¹ synthesised a number of 3-amino and 3-hydroxy coumarins which have been found to possess good bacteriostatic and fungistatic activities. This has encouraged the authors to continue the work. Some new halogenated ortho hydroxy aldehydes used as the starting materials have been synthesised and some have been prepared by methods different from those available in the literature.

The method applied in the synthesis of 3-acetamido coumarins (II, where R = -NHCOCH₃), the intermediates for the 3-amino and 3-hydroxy derivatives, is the condensation of ortho hydroxy aldehydes (I) with glycine in presence of acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate. The conditions used were similar to those of Rodighiero and Antonello² with slight variation in the time of heating and temperature. The 3-acetamido coumarins have been hydrolysed to their 3-amino derivatives (II, where R = NH₂) by heating with a mixture of (1 : 1) 50% H₂SO₄ (by volume) and acetic acid at 50-60° for 1 hr. It is interesting to note that the hydrolysis by refluxing with 3N HCl leads to the formation of the 3-hydroxy products (II, R = OH) as observed by Trivedi and Sethna³ and Chakravarti *et al.*¹ in this laboratory.

Synthesis of the aldehydes : 5-Methyl-3-bromo salicylaldehyde (I, R₂ = R₄ = H; R₃ = CH₃; R₁ = Br). This was synthesised by bromination of 5-methyl salicylaldehyde⁴ in acetic acid. The constitution of the same was proved by its synthesis from 2-bromo-*p*-cresol⁵ by Reimer Tiemann reaction.

1. D. Chakravarti and R. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, This issue.
2. G. Rodighiero and C. Antonello, *Bull. Chim. Farm.*, 1958, **97**, 592.
3. K. N. Trivedi and S. Sethna, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1817.
4. Tiemann, Schotten, *Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 773.
5. *Organic syntheses collective* Vol. 1, p. 8.

3-Methyl-5-bromo salicylaldehyde : Simple bromination of 3-methyl salicylaldehyde⁴ produced 3-methyl-5-bromo salicylaldehyde (I, $R_2 = R_4 = H$; $R_3 = Br$; $R_1 = CH_3$) identical with that prepared by Borsche Bolser⁶ by a different method.

5-chloro-4- (or 6)-methyl salicylaldehyde : (I, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = -CH_3$ or H , $R_3 = Cl$, $R_4 = H$ or CH_3). 4-Chloro-3-methyl phenol on treatment with chloroform and alkali gives an aldehyde, the structure of which may be represented by either (A) or (B).

(A)

(B)

On repeated crystallisation, the formyl derivative gave a sharp melting solid proved to be homogeneous by T.L.C. It has not yet been possible to establish the structure of the aldehyde definitely although the structure (A) is preferred to (B) in analogy with the results obtained in reactions of this type on *m*-cresol. In this communication, the aldehyde has been represented by either (A) or (B).

5-Iodo-ortho vanillin : (I, $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = I$, $R_1 = -OCH_3$) Iodination of *o*-vanillin with iodine in glacial acetic acid in presence of fused sodium acetate furnished 5-iodo-*o*-vanillin. The structure of the iodo compound was established by synthesis of the same from 5-nitro-*o*-vanillin⁷ according to Reinford and Wells⁸.

3,5-Dichloro salicylaldehyde : It has been prepared by a new method other than that described by Bitz Sptep⁹ or by Duff¹⁰. It is well known that sulphuryl chloride is used to chlorinate phenols. The authors have used this substances as a chlorinating agent for a hydroxy aldehyde. Thus 3-chloro salicylaldehyde on treatment with sulphuryl chloride gave 3,5-dichloro salicylaldehyde (I, $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_1 = R_3 = Cl$). It was further observed that salicylaldehyde on similar treatment furnished 5-chloro salicylaldehyde only, the chlorine being introduced in the *p*-position to the $-OH$ group.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 3-acetamido coumarins : An intimate mixture of the salicylaldehyde derivative (1 part), glycine (0.5 part), fused sodium acetate (1.25 parts) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (5 parts) was heated in an oil bath at 140° for one hour. The temperature was then gradually raised and heating was continued for one hour more at 160°. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to 100° and poured into water containing cracked ice. The

6. Borsche Bolser, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 2102.
7. Davis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1586.
8. Rainford and Wells, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 2500.
9. Bitz, *Sptep*, 1904, **37**, 4027.
10. Duff, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 347.

whole was kept overnight. The separated solid was washed with dil. Na_2CO_3 solution and with cold water, with a few ml of hot methanol and then crystallised from acetic acid (Table I).

3-Amino coumarins: 3-Acetamido coumarin derivative (1 g.) was suspended in a mixture of acetic acid (30 ml) and 50% H_2SO_4 (30 ml) and heated at 50–60° for one hour. The clear solution was poured into equal volume of cold water and neutralised with NaHCO_3 . The amorphous free amino product was washed and crystallised from dil. alcohol (Table II).

3-Hydroxy coumarins: 3-Acetamido coumarin derivative (2 g) in alcohol (50 ml) and 3*N* HCl (100 ml) was refluxed for five hours and filtered hot. The crystals separated on cooling were washed and crystallised from alcohol (Table III).

TABLE I

3-Acetamido coumarin derivatives

o-Hydroxy aldehyde	3-Acetamido coumarin	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis	
				Nitrogen Found	% Calcd.
3-Bromo-5-methyl-salicylaldehyde	6-methyl-8-Bromo	256–57	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{NBr}$ II, R = NHAc, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Br}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = -\text{CH}_3$	4.77	4.72
3-Methyl-5-bromo salicylaldehyde	6-bromo-8-methyl	245	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{N Br}$ II, R = NHAc, $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CH}_3$ $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{Br}$	4.61	4.72
5-Chloro-4- (or 6) methyl salicyl-aldehyde	6-chloro-7-(or 5) methyl	264–65	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ II, R = NHAc, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_3$ or H, $\text{R}_4 = \text{H}$ or $-\text{CH}_3$	5.66	5.56
5-Iodo-o-vanillin	6-iodo-8-methoxy	> 265	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{NI}$ II, R = NHAc, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$ $\text{R}_3 = \text{I}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{OCH}_3$	4.10	3.89
3,5-Dichloro salicylaldehyde	6,8-dichloro	239–40	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{NCl}_2$ II, R = NHAc, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$ $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{Cl}$	5.31	5.14

TABLE II
 3-Amino coumarins

3-Amino coumarin	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis Nitrogen %	
			Found	Calcd.
6-methyl-8-bromo	172	$C_{10}H_8O_2NBr$ II, R = NH_2 , $R_1 = Br$ $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = -CH_3$	5.39	5.51
6-bromo-8-methyl	141	$C_{10}H_8O_2NBr$ II, R = NH_2 , $R_1 = CH_3$ $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = Br$	5.56	5.51
6-chloro-7- (or 5) methyl	203	$C_{10}H_8O_2NCl$ II, R = $-NH_2$, $R_1 = H$, $R_3 = Cl$ $R_2 = CH_3$ or H , $R_4 = H$ or $-CH_3$	6.83	6.68
6-iodo-8-methoxy	170	$C_{10}H_8O_3NI$ II, R = $-NH_2$, $R_1 = -OCH_3$ $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = I$	4.66	4.41
6,8-dichloro	171	$C_9H_5O_2NCl_2$ II, R = NH_2 , $R_2 = R_4 = H$ $R_1 = R_3 = Cl$	6.37	6.08

TABLE III

3-Hydroxy coumarins

3-Hydroxy coumarin	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis	
			Found	Calcd.
6-methyl-8-bromo	215	$C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ II, R = $-OH$, $R_1 = Br$, $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = -CH_3$	Br, 31.58	Br, 31.37
6-bromo-8-methyl	237	$C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ II, R = $-OH$, $R_1 = -CH_3$ $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = Br$	Br, 31.55	Br, 31.37
6-chloro-7- (or 5) methyl	249-50	$C_{10}H_7O_3Cl$ II, R = $-OH$, $R_1 = H$, $R_3 = -Cl$, $R_2 = -CH_3$ or H , $R_4 = H$ or $-CH_3$	Cl, 16.65	Cl, 16.86
6-iodo-8-methoxy	241	$C_{10}H_7O_4I$ II, R = OH , $R_1 = -OCH_3$, $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_3 = I$	I, 39.56	I, 39.93
6,8-chloro	235	$C_9H_4O_3Cl_2$ II, R = OH , $R_2 = R_4 = H$, $R_1 = R_3 = Cl$	Cl, 30.59	Cl, 30.74

All the 3-hydroxy coumarins in alcohol give green coloration with ferric chloride and have been found to couple with diazotised aromatic amines giving brilliant red dyes.

Preparation of 5-methyl-3-bromo salicylaldehyde : To a solution of 5-methyl salicylaldehyde (15 g.) in acetic acid (30 g.), bromine (17.9 g) in acetic acid was added during 1 hr drop by drop at 30–35° with occasional shaking. The solution was stirred vigorously and allowed to stand for 1 hr, when the crystals of bromo compound began to separate. The white solid formed on pouring the reaction mixture into water was washed and crystallised from aq. alcohol as colourless long needles (14.2 g) m.p. and mixed m.p. with the aldehyde obtained from 2-bromo-*p*-cresol by the action of chloroform and alkali as shown below was 66°. Found : C, 44.40; H, 3.55; Br, 37.0%; $C_8H_7O_2Br$ requires : C, 44.65; H, 3.25; Br, 37.2%.

It gave a violet coloration with $FeCl_3$. 2 : 4-D.N.P.H. of the aldehyde crystallised from acetic acid as orange crystals melted at 289°. Found : N, 14.53%; $C_{14}H_{11}O_5N_4Br$ requires N, 14.17%.

Preparation of the above aldehyde from 2-bromo-*p*-cresol :

In a 250 ml three-necked round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser, a mercury sealed stirrer and a dropping funnel were placed 10 g of 2-bromo-*p*-cresol and 30 g of 95% alcohol. 20 g of NaOH in 45 ml of water was rapidly added. The resulting solution was heated to 60–70° with stirring on a steam bath and 13 g of chloroform was added dropwise. A gentle refluxing was maintained for 2 hrs when the sodium salt of the phenolic aldehyde began to separate.

The ethanol and chloroform were removed by distillation. The residue on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave a dark brown oil which was steam distilled. The aldehyde and some unchanged phenol began to come with the distillate very slowly as an oil. The cooled distillate was extracted with ether. After removing the major portion of ether, the ethereal solution of the oil was shaken with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite, when the bisulphite addition compound was formed. This was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and finally with ether. The white crystals of bisulphite-addition product were then treated with (1 : 10) H_2SO_4 and heated on a water bath for half an hour. On cooling, the aldehyde separated in the form of white crystals which were collected, washed and crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 66°. Yield 2 g. Found : Br, 36.91%; $C_8H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 37.2%.

Preparation of 3-methyl-5-bromo-salicylaldehyde : 3-Methyl salicylaldehyde (10 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 g) and bromine (12 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid was added drop by drop with shaking in the course of 1.5 hrs. The solution was poured into water after allowing it to stand for 2 hrs. White shining crystals of the bromo compound were collected, washed and crystallised from dil. alcohol, m.p. 68°. Yield 9.5 g.

Preparation of 5:chloro-4- (or 6) methyl salicylaldehyde : The compound was prepared from 4-chloro-3-methyl phenol by Reimer-Tiemann reaction as in the preparation of 5-methyl-3-bromo salicylaldehyde from 2-bromo-*p*-cresol. It crystallised from dil. alcohol as yellowish rhombic crystals, m.p. 68–69°. Yield 18 g. from 50 g. of phenol. Found : C, 55.91; H, 4.26%; $C_8H_7O_2Cl$ requires; C, 56.3; H, 4.1%.

The aldehyde developed an intense violet coloration with FeCl_3 .

2 : 4-D.N.P.H. derivative prepared in the usual way and crystallised from acetic acid melted at $240-42^\circ$ (d). Found : N, 15.56%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4\text{Cl}$ requires N, 15.97%.

Preparation of 5-iodo-ortho vanillin : *o*-Vanillin (6 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (64 g.). To the solution, fused sodium acetate (7 g) and iodine (12 g) were added and the reaction mixture heated at 60° for 20 hrs with occasional shaking. The reaction mixture was then poured into one litre of water. A little sodium bisulphite was added to remove the excess of unreacted iodine. The cream coloured iodo compound that separated on vigorous stirring was collected after allowing to stand for 12 hrs. The residue was washed and crystallised from dil. alcohol. On repeated crystallisation from dil. alcohol (C), the iodo compound appeared as white needles, m.p. 129° . Yield 2.1 g. Found : I, 45.26%; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{I}$ requires I, 45.68%. The compound was found to be identical with one prepared from 5-nitro-ortho vanillin by reduction, diazotisation and Sandmeyer's reaction. The iodo-*o*-vanillin in alcohol gave a bluish green coloration with FeCl_3 .

2 : 4-D.N.P.H., prepared in the usual way, crystallised from acetic acid as deep orange crystals, m.p. $277-79^\circ$. Found : N, 11.84%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4\text{I}$ requires N, 12.30%.

Preparation of 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde : 3-Chloro salicylaldehyde (7.8 g) and sulphuryl chloride (5 ml) were heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. When the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased, the excess of sulphuryl chloride was removed by a water-pump. The solid product was crystallised from acetic acid as light yellow rhombic crystals (6 g) m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 3,5-dichloro salicylaldehyde was 94° .

The antibacterial and antifungal actions of the 3-amino and 3-hydroxy coumarin derivatives will be reported in a separate communication.

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Department of Pure Chemistry,
University College of Science and Technology,
Calcutta-9.

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